

NEW INSIGHTS ON THE ROLE OF WATER IN THE HYDRATION PROCESS OF PORTLAND CEMENT (OPC)

©2023 Philippe Kunnen - Independent Researcher – Material Designer – Specialization: Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC)
Contact: phk@kunnen.io

“Nature is pleased with simplicity. And nature is no dummy”

ISAAC NEWTOWN

Abstract

Portland cement (OPC) hydration is a complex physico-chemical process and many studies have described the different phases of the overall kinetics of cement hydration. However, after decades of research and study, there are still some fundamental questions to be explicated. For example, how cement reacts with water and the origin of the slowdown of dissolution that leads to the induction (dormant) period, still have no generally accepted mechanisms proposed.

This paper attempts to address these questions by combining Dr. Gerald Pollack’s discoveries on a water structure building near hydrophilic surfaces and empirical experiments made with ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC).

It is hypothesized that when water is poured into the cement mix, the water molecules dissociate to form layers of ordered water molecules around the surface of hydrophilic (amorphous) particles present in the mix, in particular cement particles. The result is a highly organized and stable phase of water forming layers that are stacked together around the surface of cement grains with the surface becoming negatively charged. These layers of variable sizes significantly reduce the particles dissolution rate leading therefore to the occurrence of the dormant period.

Upon this new foundation, the dissolution/precipitation mechanisms of OPC and the action of heat, cold, among others, may be better understood and may prove fundamental to optimize the properties of concrete in its fresh and hardened states as well as to improve its durability.

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1. Preface

It (my approach) does not build on the “prevailing wisdom”; nor does it reflexively accept all current foundational principles as inherently valid. Instead, it returns to the root method of doing science – relying on common observation, simple logic, and the most elementary principles of chemistry and physics to build understanding.

"The Fourth Phase of Water" - Dr. Gerald Pollack (1)

My background is not formalized by a degree in chemistry or engineering, so my approach may seem unconventional. However, based on more than a decade of experience with concrete, more specifically with Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC), it is a sincere attempt to provide new insights on the role of water in the mechanisms of cement hydration.

2. Introduction

Over the past several years, I have spent much of my time trying to unravel the mysteries of phenomena observed during the mixing and hardening of my UHPC designs that contradicted the general explanations found in the scientific literature. Based on the current understanding of cement hydration, Dr. Pollack's discoveries and my observations from hundreds of tests and mixes, I believe I have accumulated enough evidence to support my proposal that water itself is most likely the key driver in the hydration mechanisms of OPC that explains, among other things, the deceleration followed by the dormant period.

In 2016, I was tasked with developing an Ultra High Performance Concrete to build wall panels of various thicknesses that would be blast resistant. Manufacturing UHPC involves specialist materials and the need for more complex mixing and curing techniques in a well-controlled environment. These requirements were not met during my assignment. I had to deal with significant temperature fluctuations, from 20°C at night to over 40°C during the day (68 to 104°F). These large fluctuations in a non-thermally insulated warehouse caused great difficulty in controlling the mixing, pouring and curing of the concrete (i.e. quick flash set, bad slump, short placement time or even unexpected swelling). In addition, when concreting in hot weather, compressive strength is adversely affected and make it difficult to obtain the last few ksi needed to achieve the required strength for UHPC generally defined as concrete with a compressive strength greater than 20 ksi.

To make a long story short, the critical strength was eventually attained and the panels successfully past the blast resistance tests (link to details & video [here](#)). However, this experience left me with a multitude of unanswered questions on the phenomenology of cement hydration when working in extreme conditions. In reading the literature to answer these questions, I was struck by the fact that many articles do a good job of describing the what and how, but rarely address the why in details. Three questions in particular left me hungry for answers:

Why does ice water improve the rheological behavior of concrete?

Why does cold improve concrete strength in the long term?

Why does cold help improve the concrete micro-structure?

I was also puzzled by the fact that although studied for more than a century, the mechanisms of Portland cement hydration, in particular the dormant period, are still highly disputed in the field. I have so often read in the literature *"we don't fully understand the mechanisms involved but..."* that

I decided to lead my own quest for answers by starting from a completely blank page. As my knowledge of concrete was mainly based on a decade of practice and field experience, I had no preconceived theoretical ideas. It probably gave me greater freedom to think outside the box.

So let's begin our journey through my readings, experiments and insights on the results.

3. Water and Dr. Pollack's 4th phase of water at-a-glance

3.1 Do we really know water?

Nobody questions today the importance of the water/cement ratio (w/c) and its influence on the properties of concrete. Neither do we ignore its role as a medium for the transport of ions in the mechanism of dissolution and precipitation. But do we really understand the nature of water itself and the full extend of its interaction within the hydration process of concrete?

Water/cement ratios of 0.45 to 0.60 are typically used in the making of regular concrete. It may sound trivial, but once we look at the molecular level and compare the size of a 0.000282 μm water molecule to a 13 μm cement particle (about 46000 times bigger), it changes the perspective. On a molecular level, water is immensely abundant in the mix and very little of its characteristics has been specifically explored with regards to cement hydration. Its role might well be underestimated.

Water is unique among chemical substances in that it displays many anomalous and unexpected behaviors. For example, if water were a "normal" material, it would freeze from the bottom up, but it does not. Upon cooling the density of liquid water increases and when its temperature reaches about 4 degrees Celsius, its density starts to decrease and the liquid freezes in a crystal that floats instead of sinking. Similarly, water is the only substance that naturally occur on Earth in all three states: solid, gas and liquid.

If you Google it, you will find that nearly 70 water anomalies have been identified to date such as the ones mentioned above, its heat capacity, diffusion or its interaction with materials that love/hate water, to name a few. Water is also electrically polarized, meaning that protons and electrons (units of charges at the atomic level) play an important role in its behavior. Could water and its anomalies play a more important role than we generally think in the hydration process of concrete?

3.2 Dr. Gerald Pollack's discovery

Dr. Pollack is a professor of bioengineering at the University of Washington and founding editor of a multidisciplinary research journal called WATER (3). He received prestigious awards and has published numerous peer-reviewed scientific papers on the subject (4).

I will not go into the details of his research, but I will briefly describe his main discovery that allowed me to conduct my experiments and develop my proposal on the mechanisms of action underlying the hydration process of Portland cement. I can only encourage you to read Dr. Pollack's publications and his book "The Fourth Phase of Water" (5) to fully grasp his new ideas.

We all learn that water has three phases: solid, liquid and solid. Dr. Pollack has made a discovery that suggests the existence of a fourth phase in the vicinity of hydrophilic surfaces, a sort of ordered, dense, alkaline, viscous phase of water.

According to Dr. Pollack's findings, most hydrophilic surfaces split the water molecules into hydroxide ions (OH^-) building an ordered phase of water adjacent to the surface while hydronium ions (H_3O^+) accumulate in the zone beyond as the hydrogen ions bond with the water molecules (Figure 1). The surface thus creates a charge separation, with the surface becoming negatively charged and the adjacent water molecules becoming positively charged.

Figure 1. Diagrammatic representation of EZ water, negatively charged, and the positively charged bulk water beyond. Hydrophilic surface at left.

© Gerald H. Pollack

That fourth phase of ordered water was named EZ for Exclusion Zone as it tends to exclude other solutes. The EZ water is not H_2O but H_3O_2 , a liquid-crystalline form of water that was found to be an intermediate between liquid water and crystalline ice. It can build on any hydrophilic surface by adding layer upon layer up to millions of molecular layers.

The layers of structured water are held together by hydrogen bonds, which are weak chemical bonds that form between hydrogen atoms and oxygen atoms in adjacent water molecules. The result is a highly organized and stable phase of water that has unique physical and chemical properties.

What immediately struck me in the face of this discovery was that if this 4th phase of water existed naturally, it would surely act on the hydration process of cement, possibly modifying the surface charge of cement grains when mixed with water. And if this change in charge were confirmed, then many unknowns about the evolution of the different phases of cement hydration, notably the induction period, could find an explanation in the 4th phase of water.

4. New insights on the role of water in cement hydration

4.1 Brief description of the known steps in the cement hydration reaction

When water is added to cement it undergoes a complex reaction involving dissolution and

precipitation of various hydrates such as calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H), calcium hydroxide (CH), ettringite and monosulfate. The progress of the chemical reactions and the different stages of hydration can be monitored by measuring the heat release and the concentration of chemical species after water is mixed with cement (Figure 2).

Figure 2. © Portland Cement Hydration by Tyler Ley, PH.D, P.E. (2)

Tyler Ley's graphs show the hydration curves as they are extensively described in the literature. Cement hydration begins with the initial period of dissolution and reaction (blue/red), followed by the induction or dormant period (green), acceleration (yellow), deceleration (purple) and finally the period of slow and continuous reaction (orange).

Stage 0 – when water is mixed with cement, a large number of ions are released from the cement particles and the heat increases rapidly.

Stage 1 – the reaction slows down as the surface of the cement particles seems to change and become less reactive. Silicon $[Si]$ in the solution decreases while calcium $[Ca^{2+}]$ increases. The heat drops.

Stage 2 – during the induction period, very little heat is given off, the hydration reaction seems to pause although Ca^{2+} concentration continues to increase.

Stage 3 – when the Ca^{2+} concentration reaches super saturation, the hydration reaction

starts again. Heat is released, calcium hydroxide, C-S-H and ettringite begin to form and initial setting occurs.

Stage 4 – As hydration products form on the surface of the cement grains, the hydration reaction slows, the heat decreases while the strengths of the concrete being formed increase.

Stage 5 – As long as water is available, the hydration process continues at a slower rate. Temperature seems to have little effect on the hydration at this point.

To this day, the steps of hydration are still being studied because no one really understands all the intricacies of the hydration reaction, especially with regard to the induction period where there is no clear explanation as to why the reaction slows to an apparent pause.

4.2 Water, cement and the 4th phase of ordered water

We know that water is polar, has the ability to ionize itself and other molecules, and behaves differently near an interface with another substance. Various experimental and theoretical studies have shown that water molecules near the interface are not like their bulk counterparts, as they assemble into layered structures and can alter the physical properties of surfaces. The literature is abundant and readily available. As it is not my intention to review these behaviors outside of cement hydration, I refer to the special issue of the American Chemical Society entitled "Water - The Most Anomalous Liquid", in particular its chapter "Water at Interfaces", as a starting point for further reading ([6](#)).

Knowing that many anomalies have been identified in relation to water, the discovery by Dr. Gerald Pollack that a fourth ordered phase of water could form on hydrophilic surfaces did not seem totally far-fetched. What really caught my attention was his description of the electrostatics at work and the fact that he described the structured water layers on the hydrophilic surface as negatively charged.

As a materials designer specializing in ultra-high performance concretes, I am well aware of the difficulty of significantly reducing the water/cement ratio to achieve the required strengths. When too little water is added to the cement during the mixing process, the cement grains clump together instead of being uniformly dispersed in the mix, which greatly affects the workability of the mix, among other things. High-range water reducers, also known as superplasticizers, are typically used to improve the workability and consistency of the mix while maintaining a low water/cement ratio.

Among the superplasticizers, polycarboxylate ethers (PCEs) are the more efficient dispersants. They are composed of a backbone that adsorb on the cement particle surface and side chains that induce the steric repulsion between the particles. Superplasticizers are adsorbed on the surface of cement particles with negatively charged ionic carboxylate groups being adsorbed onto positively charged cementitious grains. Particle dispersion is due to the electrostatic repulsion of negative charges and steric hindrance generated by the adsorbed superplasticizers.

According to the 4th phase of water theory, the structured layers of water would build around the hydrophilic cement grains. The question was then, could the layered structures assemble thick enough around the grains to induce an electrostatic repulsion between them?

Dr Pollack describes his 4th phase of water as a necessary transition phase between liquid water and ice. So I assumed that lowering the water temperature to near zero degrees Celsius would create favorable conditions for the development of EZ water. I expected that under these favorable conditions for EZ formation, the ordered layers would thicken, so that the negative repulsive forces would increase with the magnitude of the surface charge density.

4.3 Simple empirical testing

My initial experiment was implemented very simply. I prepared a UHPC mix with a water/cement ratio of 0.25 and calculated the strictly minimal amount of superplasticizer needed to achieve the right consistency. I used room temperature tap water (20°C) for the control mix. I then mixed samples keeping the water/cement ratio constant but using tap water cooled to 0°C. I repeated the experiment, gradually decreasing the amount of PCE until the mixture no longer reached a workable consistency. The result was stunning, I was able to cut in more than half the amount of superplasticizer needed to achieve the same consistency and workability as the control mix.

It is generally accepted that heat is a catalyst for the hydration reaction. The more heat, the faster the reaction; the less heat, the slower the reaction. The mechanism would be that cold temperatures slows down the setting of concrete because the chemical reactions that occur during cement hydration are exothermic. When the ambient temperature is low, the heat generated during hydration is dissipated more slowly and the rate of chemical reactions is reduced.

But if the rate of chemical reaction slows down due to the low temperature, this does not explain why the cement grains do not aggregate when half the required amount of superplasticizer is removed from the low water/cement UHPC mix. On the other hand, the idea that, due to the structured layers of the 4th phase of water, the particle surfaces become negatively charged could explain the underlying mechanism by repulsive forces: the lower the temperature, the thicker the ordered layers, the more negative repulsive forces increase with the magnitude of the surface charge density.

4.4 Water tessellation at solid surfaces

My experiment coupled with this new idea of the fourth phase of water building on cement grains seemed radical enough that I conducted a review of the literature to see if any research on cement hydration had come close to similar explanations.

There is quite an extensive literature on the tessellation of water on solid surfaces, but virtually none on the cement grains. Except for two papers concluding on an observed water tessellation on C3S surfaces (7) (8), I have not found any publications that specifically addresses this phenomenon in depth.

The tessellation effect of water at the C3S surfaces refers to the phenomenon where water molecules arrange themselves in a tessellated or hexagonal pattern around the grains during the early stages of cement hydration. But the thickness of the adsorbed water is generally considered to be one molecular layer thick.

Interestingly enough, Manzano et al. observed the formation of an ordered structure on some C3S surfaces and concluded that the *“water tessellation process preserves the crystalline order of the surface by the formation of a stable icelike monolayer, inhibiting hydration.”* (7)

However, Dr. Pollack describes the fourth phase of water as the accumulation, layer after layer, of millions of molecular layers of structured water. This observation seems to be more consistent with the results of my experiment with UHPC.

5. A new explanation of the hydration phases, especially the induction period

5.1 Initial hydration and structured water mechanism

It is hypothesized, based on Dr Pollack's discovery, that when water is poured into the cement mixture, the water molecules dissociate to form layers of ordered water molecules around the surface of the hydrophilic (amorphous) particles in the mixture, particularly the cement particles.

This rapid initial reaction would explain the first two stages of the hydration curve. At stage 0, the dissolution releases a large number of ions, releasing a lot of heat in the process, followed quickly, at stage 1, by the slowing down of the reaction due to the building of structured water on the cement grain surface, hindering its dissolution.

5.2 The induction (dormant) period

As the hydroxide ions (OH^-) build in an ordered structure on the cement grain surfaces, free hydrogen ions (H^+) are abundant beyond that zone to bond with the silica, form early C-S-H, while not enough hydroxide ions are available to bond with the calcium (Ca^{2+}). This would explain stage 2 in which silica concentration decreased while calcium continued to increase. As EZ water accumulates on the surfaces and some precipitation occurs to form the first C-S-H sites, the calcium concentration continues to increase due to the lack of sufficient free OH^- to form calcium hydroxide known as portlandite.

The non-uniform nature of the cement grains (i.e., differences in charge density at their surface) is expected to create variable width zones of structured water. The thinnest zones would break due to some form of osmosis or charge interaction in areas with opposite charge densities, explaining the release of more calcium ions during the induction period. When the level of Ca^{2+} reaches supersaturation, the remaining layers of ordered of water break and free OH^- become available to trigger the nucleation and growth of calcium hydroxides (CH).

The dissolution of the cement grains starts again and the process enters in stage 3. Dissolution can no longer be hindered by the formation of the fourth phase of water because the overall electrodynamics of the system has changed.

6. Answering three of the whys

6.1 Why does ice water improve the rheological behavior of concrete?

The rheological behavior of fresh concrete is influenced by various factors, including the water/cement ratio, cement type, aggregate characteristics, admixtures, temperature, and mixing time. Anyone on the field to place concrete will undoubtedly acknowledge that temperature and water-to-cement ratio play a major role in the rheological behavior of fresh concrete.

It is generally considered that at lower temperatures, the rate of cement hydration slows down, leading to delayed setting and hardening of concrete. This would result in increased workability or decreased viscosity of fresh concrete, as the cementitious materials react more slowly and allow for a longer time for the concrete to flow and deform under applied stress.

But my understanding has changed with my UHPC experimentation. The slow reaction alone does not explain how, with a very low cement-to-water ratio, it can compensate for the substantial reduction in superplasticizer and still allow the concrete to flow properly.

I presented a number of indications suggesting that the slowing down of the reaction would be due to the building of structured water on the cement grain surface. Therefore, I suggest that by building layers on top of layers of negatively charged structured water, a repulsive force pushing the grains apart allows fresh water to squeeze through the gaps. Under these conditions, workability increases while viscosity decreases.

In other words, the 4th phase of water would act as a repulsion mechanism similar to that of a superplasticizer. That is why, in my experiment, it was possible to significantly reduce the amount of PCE needed to achieve the same consistency and workability as the control mix.

6.2 Why does cold improve concrete strength in the long term?

Concrete is typically mixed with water at a temperature of around 20-25°C (68-77°F), and it is believed that the hydration process proceeds most efficiently when the concrete temperature is maintained within that range. If the temperature of the concrete drops below this range, the hydration reactions slow down, and the concrete may take longer to set and harden.

At the same time, if mixtures prepared in cold conditions may take longer to set and harden, at final set, they tend to have a finer, less-permeable micro-structure, leading to better long-term strength and durability.

As seen above, EZ water tend to act like superplasticizers. This 4th phase of water is a transition phase between liquid and ice. Ice begins to form around zero degrees Celsius. As my experiment suggests, the closer the temperatures are to the freezing point of water, the more EZ water forms around the hydrophilic cement particles and the higher the repulsion force between the particles. As a result, more fresh water seeps into the gaps opened by the particle separation and allows ions to flow more easily to fill the mixture more evenly. This results in more and better distribution of hydration products which will later improve the overall quality of the concrete.

6.3 Why does cold help improve the concrete micro-structure?

In the following figure of his PhD thesis on the endogenous and exogenous parameters of ordinary Portland cement influencing the hydration of tricalcium silicate (9), Farid Begarin shows that the lower the concentration of calcium hydroxides, the higher the amount of C-S-H in the initial nuclei formed:

Variation of silica concentration at the beginning of C3S hydration started in solutions with different calcium hydroxide solutions with different concentrations of calcium hydroxide. In both cases 20 g of reagents were hydrated in 1 L of solution. Curve 1 and curve 2 correspond respectively to initial calcium hydroxide concentrations in solution of 11 mmol/L and 22 mmol/L respectively. The values of $\Delta_1[\text{SiO}_2]$ and $\Delta_2[\text{SiO}_2]$ correspond to precipitation of 50 μmol and 23 μmol of C-S-H, respectively. (Garrault, S. data) (10)

As discussed above, the colder it is, the more EZ water is formed. While EZ water forms on the surface of the grains, less free OH^- are available to form portlandite (CH). The formation of C-S-H is dependent on the availability of calcium ions and silicate ions in the pore solution of the hydrated cement paste. Thus, the amount of C-S-H formed is higher because the available calcium ions in the pore solution are primarily used to form C-S-H and not portlandite during the dormant period.

The more C-S-H is formed in the initial nuclei, the finer the microstructure and the less permeable it is, which improves long-term strength and durability. Again, EZ structured water could explain why cold concreting improves the final quality of concrete.

7. Conclusion

This article is far from being exhaustive. Given the unconventional nature of my work, I simply sought to share my initial findings and thoughts.

In summary, we have seen that, in a cement mixture, water is dominant from a molecular point of view. Water is unique among chemical substances in that it displays many anomalous and unexpected behaviors. One such unexpected behavior is the tessellation of water, whose molecules arrange themselves to form a hexagonal lattice when they interact with the surface.

Dr. Pollacks' discovery resembles the tessellation mechanism, except that he observed that when water separates upon contact with hydrophilic surfaces, hydroxide ions (OH^-) accumulate in an ordered multilayer phase of water adjacent to the surface that becomes negatively charged.

My experiments with very low water/cement ratios, which require a superplasticizer to achieve good workability, have shown that under conditions that favor the development of the 4th phase of water, the amount of PCE can be greatly reduced to achieve the same result as the control mix. This tends to confirm that the surfaces of the cement grains have become negatively charged, exerting a repulsive force between them.

Based on these discoveries, I hypothesize that when water is poured into the cement mix, the water molecules dissociate to form layers of ordered water molecules around the surface of hydrophilic (amorphous) particles present in the mix, in particular cement particles. The result is a highly organized and stable phase of water forming layers that are stacked together around the surface of cement grains with the surface becoming negatively charged. These layers of variable sizes significantly reduce the particles dissolution rate leading therefore to the occurrence of the dormant period. Thus, a poorly understood mechanism underlying cement hydration find a simple and insightful explanation.

Further empirical experiments I conducted with water and cement based on Dr. Pollack's theories definitely convinced me that there are new avenues of discovery to explore. Finding out the true nature of water and unraveling its mysteries could be key to making concrete a better material for the future.

8. Acknowledgment

I dedicate my article to Dr. Gerald Pollack of the University of Washington for his courageous stand not to rest on accepted theories to build new foundations in our understanding of water, and Tyler Ley of Oklahoma State University for sharing with us his passion for concrete, his original approach to explore its underlying mechanisms, all expressed in a very didactic way.

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